

Biomedical Signals Based User Authentication System

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Abstract

User authentication is becoming more and more interesting and can be implemented in different ways. Conventional authentication systems are getting replaced by adaptive continuous authentication systems. Biometric has revolutionized the authentication technology but still static passwords are in use, despite of their certain issues. Biometric can identify and authenticate users given their physiological and behavioral traits. Fingerprint and face recognition have gained popularity in individual verification. However, these authentication systems have certain flaws such as fingerprint fabrication and external barriers. This paper focuses on some more reliable and advanced AI-based techniques for user authentication, which unlike other biometrics, confirms person is real and alive. This study focuses authentication based on one-dimensional physiological signals such as Electrocardiogram (ECG), Electroencephalogram (EEG), and Electromyogram (EMG). The approach is to familiarize with these secure and convenient user authentication methods which can be used in various applications.

Keywords

User authentication, ElectroCardioGram (ECG), Electroencephalogram (EEG), Electromyogram(EMG)

1. Introduction

One-dimensional biomedical signals constitute another category of biometric user authentication as they encompass signals. Biomedical signals such as the electrocardiogram (ECG) or electroencephalogram (EEG), electromyogram (EMG) can be used as physiological biometric characteristics [1]. These biometric confirm that each person has distinct physiological features due to genetic variances. Though every biometric has its own strengths and weaknesses, these biometrics are used to obtain universality, measurability, uniqueness and robustness.

- (1) Universality (every person should have that characteristic)
- (2) Measurability (allowing for future comparison)
- (3) Uniqueness (no two people should be exactly same in terms of that characteristic)
- (4) Robustness (strong characteristic)

Bio signal based authentication works by collecting and analyzing the signals of the individual and comparing them to the stored template of that person's signals. These authentication

systems have several advantages over other types of authentication methods, including high accuracy and security, as these signals are difficult to replicate or fake. Additionally, bio signal based authentication is non-invasive and does not require physical contact or the use of any devices, making it a convenient and user-friendly authentication method. In the health-care field, bio signal based authentication is particularly useful for securing access to medical devices, such as implantable devices or medical equipment, and for ensuring patient safety and privacy. Additionally, bio signal based authentication can help prevent medical identity theft and protect sensitive medical information. Though biomedical signals based user authentication is a promising technology, it has the potential to enhance security and privacy in various fields, including healthcare, finance, law enforcement and many more.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows. Section 2 provides architecture of biometric system. Section 3 explores some popular bio-medical signals used in user authentication. Section 4 highlights on the major issue during authentication and discusses the different models which can be used along with their advantages and disadvantages and then we finally conclude.

2. Architecture of Biometric system

2.1 Data Collection:

The authentication system can be used in two modes: verification (authentication) or identification (recognition). The verification mode is used to validate an asserted identity. It is used to determine whether a person is whom he or she claims to be. This mode is used to authenticate a mobile user. The score is compared to a preset threshold during verification, and the claimed identity is approved if the score is more significant. The identification method is used to categorize and identify an unknown identity. It answers inquiries such as “who is this person?” or “is this person in the database?” This method is commonly used in cybercrime. During identification, the highest matching score is taken into account.

Biometric design is divided into two stages: enrollment and authentication. The data are gathered, analyzed, and saved as a reference template throughout the enrollment phase. The test sample is checked against the stored reference template(s) in the authentication phase to ascertain the similarity or dissimilarity score provided by machine learning technique(s) against a predetermined threshold. Data are actually collected through a sensing device, wearables etc. After recording the signals, they are pre-processed before feature extraction. Finally, the samples are saved in a feature database and categorized using classifiers such as decision trees, support vector machines, CNN, etc. and then the assessment criteria will be used to make a choice.

2.2 Feature Engineering:

The process of obtaining relevant features from raw data that can be utilized to train a machine learning model is known as feature engineering. This is a crucial action performed throughout the enrollment and authentication phases. This may entail feature extraction and selection, followed by a training classification based on the extracted features. Machine learning algorithms are used for this approach and the advance technique is to use deep learning

approaches that can self-learn useful features from input signals. Previous research on traditional machine learning algorithms has revealed certain flaws. They require a highly complicated foundation to construct the authentication mechanism. As a result, many characteristics will be retrieved from signals. Too many features (the curse of dimensionality) will need additional training time and memory space, thus impeding real-time implementation. Machine learning algorithms may also struggle with massive test datasets. This also has the issue of overfitting, which can lead to performance loss. Deep learning algorithms provide a more straightforward framework for an authentication system [2, 3].

2.3 Feature Selection:

Using several features and varied combinations can increase classification efficiency, but rigorous feature selection is also required to keep errors to a minimum.

2.4 Evaluation Matrices:

A standard tool for assessing how accurately a model might forecast a particular validation collection is the confusion matrix (CM). The CM includes comparable columns and rows that display the test dataset labels and the actual class. For each validation sample, the projected values show the proportion of accurate and inaccurate forecasts or categorizations. The number of adequately classified positive samples is known as True Positive, while the amount of successfully foreseen negative instances is known as Negative Cases. False Positives are forecasts in which the item was marked as positive but was not. False negatives are unfavorable outcomes that have a good appearance. Numerous metrics, including accuracy rate, recall, precision, F1 score, sensitivity, the area under the curve, and specificity, were used to assess the effectiveness of the AI-based algorithms. The following Equations (1)–(4) determined each model's accuracy rate, recall, precision, F1 score, sensitivity, and specificity [4].

$$\text{Precision} = \text{TP}/(\text{TP} + \text{FP}), \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Recall} = \text{TP}/(\text{TP} + \text{FN}), \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Accuracy} = (\text{TP} + \text{TN})/(\text{TP} + \text{TN} + \text{FP} + \text{FN}), \quad (3)$$

$$\text{F1 Score} = 2 * (\text{Precision} * \text{Recall}) / (\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}), \quad (4)$$

The Receiver Operating characteristic (ROC) graph is a measurement tool for classifiers concerns. Essentially, it isolates the “signal” from the “background” by plotting the true positive rate (TPR) against the false positive rate (FPR) at different threshold levels. The capacity of a predictor to differentiate among classes is measured by the Area Under the Curve (AUC), which is used as a summarization of a Prediction model. A model having a higher AUC value means the model is efficient at predicting between FPR and TPR.

3. BIOMEDICAL SIGNAL IDENTIFICATION METHODS

3.1 ECG

The electrocardiogram (ECG) is a graph that reproduces the electrical activity of the heart, obtained by placing electrodes over suitable parts of the body (Figure 1).

Figure 1 Electrodes position for ECG recording

The idea behind using ECG as a biometric is that the electrical signals produced by the heart are unique to each individual, much like fingerprints or iris patterns. Although its deployment in real applications is not as popular as most established biometric traits, ECG signals have been obtained satisfactory accuracy to perform biometric recognition in a wide range of applications [5]. ECG signals are well adopted for performing user authentication in the smart health network, including patients, doctors, attendants, etc. Among physiological signal analysis techniques, ECG stands out on account of its maturity and diffusion. ECG signals provide higher security as they are measured inside the body, making it difficult to simulate or copy [6]. ECG signals can be easily captured from fingers [7] or through wearable devices [8] which enhance their applications in various fields [9]. But ECG-based biometric systems also have to cope with a range of issues [10], including: (i) high inter-subject variability - can vary significantly between individuals; (ii) high intra-subject variability - can vary significantly over time within same individual(mental, emotional or physical changes); (iii) data privacy - can contain sensitive information which could be used for malicious purposes; (iv) signal quality - can be affected by various factors such as noise, movement artifacts, and electrical interference.

3.1.1 Feature Types

ECG signal (figure 2) is made up of various waveforms that can be divided into five main segments that correspond to various cardiac operations: atrial depolarization (P wave), ventricular repolarization (T wave), and ventricular depolarization (QRS complex), the time between the end of QRS complex and the start of the T wave (ST segment) and the time between the start of P wave and the start of QRS complex (PR interval).

ECG signal is typically recorded using a standardized format, known as 12-lead ECG, which provides a comprehensive view of the heart's electrical activity from different angles. In ECG-based biometric authentication, specific features of the ECG signal are used to identify an individual. These features are typically extracted from the ECG signal using signal processing techniques and are then used as the basis for biometric recognition. Besides the above specified features, Heart rate variability (HRV) which is the variation in time between successive heartbeats and is a measure of the autonomic nervous system

Figure 2: ECG Signal

activity is highly individual-specific and can be used for biometric recognition. ECG morphological features include the peak-to-peak interval, the slope of the ECG waveform, and the width of the QRS complex, among others is also used for biometric recognition. According to the feature extraction manner, existing ECG identification methods can be typically divided into two categories which are the fiducial and the non-fiducial [11]: (i) The fiducial refers to methods that extract ECG features based on fiducial points, e.g., P, Q, R, S, and T. Fiducial features are amplitudes of P, Q, R, S, and T waves, the temporal interval between wave boundaries, the area of waves, and the slope information [12]; (ii) for the non-fiducial [13], no peak detection is required during feature extraction. The most prevalent non-fiducial features include frequency domain features which are coefficients or parameters obtained by certain specific transformations, such as wavelet transform and statistical features, which are converted from ECG waveforms by statistical methods, such as principal component analysis (PCA).

Once these features have been extracted from the ECG signal, they are used as input to a machine learning algorithm, such as a support vector machine or a neural network, which is

trained to recognize the unique ECG patterns of each individual. The machine learning algorithm then compares the ECG features of the current user to the reference ECG features stored in a database and makes a decision about whether the user is the legitimate user or an impostor.

3.2. EEG

EEG is a measure of the electrical activity of the brain. It is commonly used to diagnose neurological conditions and monitor brain activity. In emerging biometrics system, EEG can be used to create a unique brain signature for an individual, which then can be used for identification purposes.

The recording of brain signals is done by placing multiple electrodes on participant's scalp using a special cap that holds the electrodes in place. The placement of electrodes depends on the research question and the area of the brain that is being studied [14]. Once the electrodes are in place, the participant is asked to sit still and relax with their eyes closed or open. The EEG signal is recorded for a specific amount of time, usually ranging from a few minutes to an hour. The EEG signals are electrical spikes that result from neural activity in the brain cortex. These signals are recorded from the scalp of the subject in a non-invasive manner [15]. The recorded EEG signal is processed to remove any noise or artifacts such as blinking of eye that can interfere with the analysis. The signal is then divided into different frequency bands, such as alpha, beta, theta, and delta waves, depending on the research question. The processed EEG data is analyzed using various statistical and signal processing techniques to extract meaningful information about brain activity. The analysis can involve comparing the EEG data between different conditions or groups of participants, correlating the EEG data with behavioral or physiological measures, or using machine learning algorithms or deep learning algorithm to classify different brain states.

3.2.1 Feature Types

EEG (electroencephalogram) signals can be decomposed into several frequency bands or features that are associated with different aspects of brain activity. Here are some of the most commonly used feature types of EEG (depicted in figure 3):

Delta waves: Delta waves are low-frequency (0.5-4 Hz) EEG waves that are usually associated with deep sleep and unconsciousness.

Theta waves: Theta waves are medium-frequency (4-8 Hz) EEG waves that are often associated with relaxed mental states, daydreaming, and meditation. These waves represent the beginning stages of sleep.

Alpha waves: Alpha waves are medium-frequency (8-13 Hz) EEG waves that are usually associated with relaxed wakefulness and closed-eye resting states. Auditory and mental arithmetic tasks with the eyes closed lead to strong alpha waves.

Beta waves: Beta waves are high-frequency (13-30 Hz) EEG waves that are often associated with active cognitive processing, attention, and alertness.

Gamma waves: Gamma waves are very high-frequency (>30 Hz) EEG waves that are often associated with higher cognitive functions, such as perception, attention, and memory.

Event-related potentials (ERPs): ERPs are time-locked EEG signals that are elicited by specific events or stimuli, such as visual, auditory, or somatosensory stimuli. ERPs can provide insights into the neural processes underlying sensory perception, attention, memory, and language processing.

Coherence: Coherence is a measure of the degree of synchronization between EEG signals recorded from different brain regions. Coherence can provide insights into the functional connectivity between different brain regions and the neural networks underlying cognitive processes.

These feature types are used to study a wide range of cognitive, sensory, and motor processes and also provides valuable information about different aspects of brain activity.

Awake with mental activity

Beta
14-30 Hz

Awake and resting

Alpha
8-13 Hz

Sleeping

Theta
4-7 Hz

Deep sleep

Delta
< 3.5 Hz

1 second

Figure 3: EEG Rhythms

3.3 EMG

EMG signal is an electrical signal generated when the muscles move, which can be used in various fields such as motion recognition, personal identification, and disease diagnosis. The EMG signal is generally acquired at the skin's surface and is a complex mix of electrical signals produced as a result of neuromuscular activity, as well as the recording environment [16, 17]. Compared to other bio-electric signals, EMG signals vary widely subject to age, gesture style, muscle strength, motor unit paths and skin-fat layer [17]. The electrical signals are measured by means of electrodes attached to the skin and are non-invasive. It has a wide range of frequency band and voltage values from 5 to 10,000 Hz. The raw EMG data is collected which provides an overview of the contractions and movements of the examined muscles. The raw EMG signal is bipolar with a symmetrical distribution of positive and negative voltage values. Figure 4 shows the EMG signal waveform, as raw signals and the filtered EMG signals.

3.3.1 Feature Types

Feature extraction is an important step in user authentication process, to transform raw signal into relevant form. There are three main categories of features important for the operation of an EMG based control system which includes time domain, frequency domain, and the time-frequency domain [18].

Time domain features: These features describe the amplitude, frequency, and duration of the EM signal [6]. Examples of time domain features include root mean square (RMS), mean absolute value (MAV), and waveform length (WL). Features in this domain are particularly used for EMG pattern recognition.

Root Mean Square (RMS): The Root Mean Square (RMS) is modeled as the amplitude or intensity of an EMG signal. RMS is related to the muscle activity and contractile properties, such as muscle activation level, muscle fatigue, and muscle strength [7].

Figure 4: EMG Signal

$$RMS = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N |x_i|^2} \quad (6)$$

(1)

Mean Absolute Value (MAV): The Mean Absolute Value (MAV) is a method of detecting and gauging muscle contraction levels without considering the polarity or direction of the signal. It is expressed as the moving average of the full-wave rectified EMG signal [7, 8].

$$MAV = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N |x_i| \quad (2)$$

(2)

Waveform Length (WL): The Waveform length (WL) is intuitively a measure of the total amount of changes in the amplitude of the signal over time, and can be used as an indicator of muscle activity, muscle fatigue, and other physiological or pathological conditions.

$$WL = \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} |x_{i+1} - x_i| \quad (7)$$

(3)

Frequency domain features: These features describe the spectral content of the EMG signal. Examples of frequency domain features include median frequency (MF), spectral moments, and power spectral density (PSD).

Time-frequency domain features: These features combine time and frequency domain information to provide a more complete picture of the EMG signal. Examples of time-frequency domain features include wavelet transform, short-time Fourier transform (STFT), and continuous wavelet transform (CWT).

Along with biometric authentication, these features can be used in various applications such as clinical diagnosis, rehabilitation, and prosthetics control.

4. Security Concern during Authentication

Data security and privacy always remain a point of concern during authentication. In order to dynamically protect systems from cyber threats, many cybersecurity experts are turning to Artificial Intelligence (AI), Machine Learning (ML), and eventually, Deep Learning (DL). DL is a prominent ML method, and ML is a portion of AI, but all refers to leveraging automated learning from data to improve performance on some set of tasks (figure 5).

Figure 5: AI vs ML vs DL

Figure 6 shows how AI is used in cybersecurity, but of course, attackers find ways to thwart these AI and may even use AI to attack systems [19]. When it comes to cybersecurity, ML can potentially have a real lasting impact on cybersecurity by analyzing patterns in malware behavior more quickly, accurately, and efficiently making it less expensive.

Figure 6: AI in cybersecurity

ML can solve the issue of identifying legitimate users and through a continuous authentication system to detect any violence [20]. An insider, such as a disgruntled employee, can sell confidential data for money or disseminate them to cause harm to the system. Besides insider attacks, many other attacks, such as tampering, Ransomware, DoS, DDoS, etc., can be detected by ML models. Continuous authentication will periodically check the legitimacy of the person/device during the session, preventing impersonation at any time during the session. Additionally, it also speeds up the authentication process. In continuous authentication, dynamic data that are very difficult to mimic are used. Dynamic authentication uses dynamic traits, such as biometric data, that can change in each session to authenticate users. ML provides the key solution to using dynamic authentication. ML can be established to lessen security traps and address security issues.

Considering the importance of data confidentiality, the authentication scheme must be accurate and reliable. False negative rate (FNR) refers to intruders authenticated wrongly and false positives rate (FPR) denotes legitimate persons that are not identified. Both FNR and FPR are important to make an outstanding authentication scheme and should not exceed a few percentages. On the other hand, datasets for authentication are mostly class imbalance that poses serious difficulties to most ML algorithms and decreases their accuracy [21]. Overcoming this

problem in the context of multimodal biometric authentication is a major challenge for many models.

Furthermore, enrolling new users is an undeniable need for an authentication scheme. Some ML-based authentication models cannot be updated or adopt new users, and we have to train the model from scratch when enrolling a new user. This trend is not cost-effective for authentication platforms and needs more attention in updating after deployment [22]. Permanency is another requirement to be considered, it may cause issues in model performance when entities' features change over time, such as face aging with time. This is a privilege for an ML algorithm to be robust against noisy data and handle some changes in upcoming data.

A primary category of ML-based authentication models uses multi-class classifiers to create a supervised scheme. A wide range of algorithms, such as Naïve Bayes (NB), Support Vector Machine (SVM), decision tree (DT), Random Forest (RF), Artificial Neural Network (ANN), deep neural network (DNN) has been used widely in this area [23, 24]. The main advantage of this is the ability to handle multi-users at the same time. Therefore, these models are scalable, while highly raising the number of registered users may decrease the model performance. On the other hand, the downside is the cost of enrolling a new user by training the model from scratch or updating the system. The permanency of the model depends on the supervised classifier that has been trained in this architecture.

Since most multi-class classifiers are affected by imbalanced datasets, one-class classifiers have been proposed as another category to address this problem. In these models, a one-class classifier, such as a one-class SVM (OC-SVM) is trained using legitimate and illegitimate samples [25, 26]. One-class classification is a machine learning technique used to identify anomalies or outliers in a dataset by training a model on only one class of data, typically the normal class. The main advantage of one-class classifiers is that they are not sensitive to imbalanced class conditions. One-class classifiers are designed to identify anomalies in data by learning only the normal class. As a result, they tend to have high specificity, meaning they have a low false-positive rate. They are often robust to changes in the data distribution, making them suitable for real-world applications where the data distribution may change over time. Such models are useful for personal devices, while the main bottleneck needs to train a model for each user in multi-user systems; therefore, they are not scalable.

The next category uses an unsupervised method in training an autoencoder just based on samples of the intended identity [27]. Autoencoders can be used for feature extraction in biomedical signal authentication. By learning a compressed representation of the input signal, autoencoders can identify relevant features for authentication without explicit feature engineering. Autoencoders can reduce the high dimensionality of biomedical signal data, making it easier to

process and analyze. Autoencoders are known to be robust to noise, which is a common problem in biomedical signals. Autoencoders can scale to large datasets, making them useful in applications where data is abundant.

Using lazy models is another trend in the authentication. Lazy models do not contain a training phase and just save the instances until an assessment. When we want to authenticate a new instance, it should be assessed online with the available samples. Therefore, to enroll a new user or update its profile, it is just needed to add new instances to the repository, while the computational complexity will rise due to the need for more distance calculation. Furthermore, they are not sensitive to imbalanced class conditions. Lazy models can handle large datasets and can adapt to new data without requiring retraining. They are often robust to changes in the data distribution and can adapt to non-stationary data. The drawback of such methods is the calculation burden while using the model [28].

Deep learning models, such as convolutional neural networks (CNNs) and recurrent neural networks (RNNs), have gained popularity in biomedical signal authentication due to their ability to learn complex features and patterns from large datasets. Deep models can also select or extract the best feature set and do not need a separate preprocessing for feature selection, or extraction. Deep learning models can scale to large datasets, making them useful in applications where data is abundant. Despite many advantages, deep models need more data than ML methods to enhance training and avoid overfitting.

Siamese networks are a type of deep learning architecture that is commonly used in biomedical signal authentication. Siamese networks learn to identify similarities and differences between pairs of signals, which make them useful for tasks such as biometric identification and classification. Siamese networks need only one recorded sample from each entity for the subsequent comparison, which is much more realistic and feasible for authentication schemes. Siamese networks are robust to variations in signal quality and can identify similarities and differences in signals even when the signals have been distorted or corrupted. Siamese networks can be easily scaled to handle large datasets and can be trained on a wide range of biomedical signals [29]. In particular various methods have been proposed to enhance the security of system. Table 1, below shows the use of different machine learning models along with their advantages and disadvantages.

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Table 1: Pros and Cons of classifiers

Conclusion

Biomedical signal-based user authentication is a promising approach for enhancing the security of various systems. The use of physiological signals, such as electroencephalogram (EEG), electrocardiogram (ECG), and electromyogram (EMG), as biometric identifiers has shown great potential in ensuring the identity of users. The use of biomedical signals for user authentication has several advantages over traditional methods, such as passwords or PINs, which can be easily hacked or stolen. Biomedical signals are unique to each individual and cannot be easily replicated or forged, providing a high level of security. The paper has covered various techniques for biomedical signal-based user authentication, including feature extraction, signal classification, and machine learning algorithms. These techniques have demonstrated high accuracy and robustness in identifying users based on their unique physiological characteristics. However, there are still some challenges that need to be addressed, such as the collection and processing of the biomedical signals and the need for specialized equipment to acquire the signals. Additionally, the ethical and privacy concerns associated with the use of physiological signals as biometric identifiers need to be carefully considered.

Several type of attacks has been reported in case of these automated authentication systems, which open a wide scope for researchers to build a safe and secure biometric systems taking into consideration the existing problems in present biometric systems. This paper also summarizes the various models which can be used along with a brief description of their advantages and disadvantages. This paper indicates that biomedical signal-based user authentication is a promising approach for enhancing the security of various systems, and further research in this area has the potential to lead to new and innovative authentication methods.

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